

Shear-induced molecular fragmentation decreases the bioaccessibility of fully gelatinized starch and its gelling capacity

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Abstract

This work provides information on the feasibility of molecular shear scissions that promote interactions resulting in slowly digestible foods. Extrusion using nine different Specific Mechanical Energy (SME) was performed to obtain amylose and amylopectin with different hydrodynamic radius (R_h) and molecular weight (M_w) from banana starch. The work also aims to find a potential size threshold that decrease starch bio-accessibility through the formation of structural assemblies. Shear-induced fragmentation enabled molecules to get in closer proximity promoting interactions that caused a 36 % reduction in their digestion rate. Results suggested that the nature of the structurally-driven slowly digestible starch is mostly due to molecular interactions involving amylopectin, which do not necessarily worsen the food mechanical properties. The R_h and M_w threshold to significantly decrease starch bio-accessibility was estimated to be in the range of 54.3-58.9 nm and 9.9×10^6 - 17.1×10^6 g/mol, respectively, which was attained in the SME range 177-274 kJ/kg.

Keywords: Banana starch; extrusion; digestion; retrogradation; rheology; glycemic index

1 Introduction

Diets having a high glycemic carbohydrate to protein ratio have been recently reported to improve health and longevity (Seidelmann, et al. 2018). This interesting finding contrasts with the poor health outcomes attributed to a diet consisting of foods with high glycemic index (Ceriello & Colagiuri, 2008), i.e., foods promoting a spike in post-meal blood glucose. The high glycemic index of many foods is mainly originated by the amorphous structure of starch caused by its gelatinization, which results in far greater availability of α -amylase binding sites and makes the substrate more susceptible to enzyme hydrolysis (Baldwin et al., 2015). Since in excess of water ($\geq 20\%$ water) most starches gelatinize approximately in a range from 54 to 78 °C (Vamadevan, Bertoft, & Seetharaman, 2013), slowing-down the digestion rate of fully gelatinized starches could have a major impact on consumers providing them a healthy diet alternative along the pleasure experience of consuming indulgent foods (Pozharliev, Verbeke, Van Strien, & Bagozzi, 2015).

Starch digestion rate of fully gelatinized starch, and, therefore, its bioaccessibility, is reduced during storage due to retrogradation (re-association of dispersed starch molecules through H-bonding), with an extent that depends on the main constituents involved in the reassociation. Amylose (AM) forming double helical structures (retrograded amylose) is known to be enzymatically resistant and yield resistant starch (RS) (Haralampu, 2000), whereas retrograded amylopectin (AP) has been associated with the formation of slowly digestible starch (SDS) [Cui & Oates, 1997; Zhang, Sofyan, & Hamaker, 2008]. Past and recent works on amylopectin molecular structure-digestion relationships have shown interesting findings that position some starches as potential candidates to promote slowly-digestible structures. Specifically, slowly digestible starch structures during storage are particularly formed in amylopectins with: 1) high proportions of long chains, i.e., higher molar ratio of long to short chains (Benmoussa,

Moldenhauer, & Hamaker, 2007; Martinez, et al., 2018); 2) chains with longer average length (Martinez et al., 2018; Roman, Gomez, Hamaker, & Martinez, 2019; Zhang et al., 2008) and/or; 3) induced lower molecular sizes through processes such as acid-conversion or high shear extrusion (Martinez et al., 2018; Roman et al., 2019). Banana starch is one type of starch having a natural molecular structure that can form structurally-driven SDS (SSDS) through retrogradation. Roman et al. (2019) using fully gelatinized bread crumb as a model system, showed, for first time, that the propensity of banana amylopectin to form SSDS was further improved by the reduction of its molecular size through extrusion (a chemically free and cost-effective technology). Specifically, through high shear extrusion, the SSDS content in fully gelatinized bread crumbs containing 20 % banana starch (flour basis) increased by 85 % with an amylopectin molecular size reduction from 275×10^6 to 4.5×10^6 g/mol. This result was attributed to the enhanced interactions of starch molecules having lower molecular size, which are more mobile and easily aligned during retrogradation. However, information about the minimum size reduction, i.e. a threshold molecular size, to result in a significant decrease in the digestion rate of gelatinized starch remains unexplored. In addition, the effects of extrusion cooking at different shear conditions on the molecular size/weight of banana starch has never been studied. The gained information could provide insights on the limitation/feasibility and efficiency of the extrusion technology to reduce the size of starch molecules. This is particularly relevant considering the existence of a maximum stable size/weight that can be achieved by shear scission of amylopectin through extrusion (Liu, Halley, & Gilbert, 2010). That is, for a given shear environment, no further shear degradation occurs for molecules smaller than this threshold size. In fact, the maximum stable molecular weight and hydrodynamic radius (R_h) for extruded maize amylopectin was reported to be around 3.5×10^6 g/mol (Brümmer, Meuser, van Lengerich, & Niemann, 2002)

and 50 nm (Li, Hasjim, Xie, Halley, & Gilbert, 2014; Liu et al., 2010), respectively, which is not far from the size attained after extrusion in previous work of our group (Roman et al., 2019).

Retrogradation has been extensively studied because of its influence in bread staling (Gray & BeMiller, 2003) and gel syneresis (Hoover & Manuel, 1995). Thus, promoting retrogradation to reduce starch bioaccessibility could be seen, in principle, as deleterious in terms of food texture quality. However, extrusion has shown to decrease the tendency of maize, rice and wheat flours to form interactions promoting the formation of starch gel-like structures during storage, which are responsible for controlling the mechanical properties and texture of foods (Roman, Gomez, Hamaker & Martinez, 2018a; Liu et al., 2017). This functional advantage of extruded starchy-materials has been attributed to the size reduction of both amylose and amylopectin. Therefore, investigations on the effects of shear induced fragmentation of amylose and amylopectin on the formation of SSDS should be holistically conducted including studies on the additional benefit of promoting texture enhancing gel-like structures.

The objective of this study was, thus, to obtain mechanistic understanding on the fragmentation of banana starch subjected to different extrusion conditions in terms of shear and its effect on the creation of SSDS and gel-like structures of fully gelatinized materials. Results of this work are expected to serve as the basis for the assessment of high shear extrusion as a feasible strategy to create clean label polymer ingredients using an energy efficient and sustainable technology to be incorporated into processed starchy foods with slow glycemc response.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Starch from green lady finger bananas (moisture 6.3%, protein 3.2%, resistant starch 42.2%, and particle size 268 μm) was purchased from Natural Evolution (Walkamin, Queensland, Australia). Proximate analysis of the starch was determined according to the AACC methods (AACC, 2015) for moisture (44-15.02), protein content (46–30.01) using a Leco TruSpec device (Leco, St. Joseph, MI, USA) and resistant starch content (32-40.01) using the RS Megazyme assay kit. Particle size, $d(4,3)$ value, was measured with a laser diffraction particle size analyzer (Mastersizer 3000, Malvern Instruments, Ltd., Worcestershire, UK). The unit chain length distribution and composition of banana starch was reported in Roman et al. (2019) using size exclusion chromatography after debranching with isoamylase from *pseudomonas*. The starch exhibited a 30.4 % amylose ratio, amylose chains of DP, at peak maximum, of 1026 glucose units (GU), amylopectin short (A and B1) and long (B2 and B3) chains of DP, at peak maximum, of 17 and 43 GU, respectively. The unit chain length distribution of the different extruded starches was not analyzed because no detectable differences have been reported after extrusion treatment (Li et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2010). Considering that amylopectin is a highly branched polymer with some chain segments lacking branching points, a small number of cleavages of unbranched segments would not significantly change the chain length distribution. In other words, only a small number of bond cleavages would be needed to create a drastic reduction in the molecular size of amylopectin.

Protease from *Streptomyces griseus* (type XIV), porcine pancreatic α -amylase (Grade 1-A, A6255, EC 3.2.1.1) and para-hydroxybenzoic acid hydrazide (PAHBAH, H9882) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, GR for analysis ACS)

and lithium bromide (ReagentPlus) were purchased from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA) and Beantown Chemical (Hudson, NH, USA), respectively. Phosphate buffered saline (10X Powder, pH 7.4) was purchased from Fisher BioReagents (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Extrusion treatment

Banana starch was extruded in a Krupp Werner and Pfleiderer ZSK-25 twin-screw extruder (Ramsey, NJ, USA) with co-rotating and closely intermeshing screws of 25 mm diameter and length to diameter ratio (L/D) of 25. The screw geometry consisted of forward screws with two different pitch and two combined sets of mixing disks coupled to reverse screw elements. The die head consisted of two circular dies of 4 mm diameter and the feed input flow rate was 5 kg/h. Barrel temperatures of the five barrel sections were kept constant, from the feeding to the die zone, at 40, 60, 90, 120 and 130 °C, respectively. Banana starch was subjected to 9 different extrusion treatments, where screw speed and water input were modified as specified in Table 1 to provide different Specific Mechanical Energy (SME) values. Briefly, 3 water input flow rates (23, 18.5 and 14 g/min to obtain a total moisture content of 32, 27 or 22%, respectively) and 3 screw speeds (120, 200 and 280 rpm) were selected to result in a range of SME from 177 to 394 kJ/kg. Extruded products were dried overnight at 60 °C in an air convection oven, and then ground with a pin mill to a particle size below 200 microns. The obtained extruded starches were stored in air-tight plastic containers and held at room temperature until further analysis. It is worth noting that the drying temperature (60 °C) used to dry the extruded products overnight was below the initial temperature for starch gelatinization (71.74 °C) of banana starch as previously reported in Roman et al. (2019). Therefore, no gelatinization is expected to occur as a result of the drying process.

Table 1. Extrusion conditions used for processing of banana starch.

Code	Feed moisture content (%)	Screw speed (rpm)	SME (kJ/kg)
Native banana	-	-	0
EB 1	32	120	177
EB 2	32	200	230
EB 3	32	280	274
EB 4	27	120	204
EB 5	27	200	285
EB 6	27	280	327
EB 7	22	120	280
EB 8	22	200	330
EB 9	22	280	394

2.2.2 Molecular size and weight of starch molecules

The molecular size distributions of amylose and amylopectin from the 10 starches were analyzed in triplicate following the method reported by Cave, Seabrook, Gidley, and Gilbert (2009) with minor modifications as reported previously in Martinez et al. (2018). Protein was first removed by treating the starch with a protease and a sodium bisulfite solution, each followed by centrifugation using a method described elsewhere (Tran et al., 2011). The treated starch was then dissolved in a DMSO–0.5% (w/w) Lithium/Bromide solution (DMSO/LiBr), and the remaining non-starch polysaccharide components were removed by precipitating the starch using ethanol (6 volumes of DMSO/LiBr) followed by centrifugation at 4000 g for 10 min. The precipitated starch was redissolved in DMSO/LiBr at 80 °C overnight. The molecular size distributions of fully branched starches from native and extruded banana starches were analyzed using a size exclusion chromatography (SEC) system (Agilent 1260 series, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a refractive index detector (RID, RID-10A, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). Size separation of branched starch molecules was carried out using GRAM pre-column, GRAM 30 and GRAM 3000 columns (PSS GmbH, Mainz, Germany) in a column oven at 80 °C, and starch molecules were eluted using the DMSO/LiBr solution at 0.3 mL/min. A series of pullulan

standards with molecular weights ranging from 342 to 2.35×10^6 were used for calibration, allowing elution volume to be converted to hydrodynamic volume (V_h , or the corresponding radius, R_h) using the Mark–Houwink equation (Vilaplana & Gilbert, 2010).

It is well known that branched polymers, such as amylopectin, do not exhibit a unique relationship between their size and molar mass, which means that a sample perfectly uniform in size may contain a range of molar masses (Gidley et al., 2010). In this regard, distributions obtained from different detectors may provide complementary information. Hence, the molecular weight (M_w) of banana starch molecules was also measured using a multi-angle light scattering detector (MALS, Dawn Heleos, Wyatt Technology, Santa Barbara, CA, USA) containing a K5-cell as described previously (Roman et al., 2019). Data was analyzed with the ASTRA software (version 4.72.03, Wyatt Technology Corporation, Goleta, CA, USA) and by using a second-order Berry plot procedure. The specific refractive index increment (dn/dc) was assumed to be 0.066 ml/g as usually reported for starch dissolved in DMSO (Roman et al., 2019; Zhong, Yokoyama, Wang, & Shoemaker, 2006) and the second virial coefficient (A_2) was assumed to be negligible (Roman et al., 2019; Yoo & Jane, 2002).

2.2.3 Thermal and rheological properties of gelatinized and retrograded samples

2.2.3.1 Thermal transitions of native and retrograded banana starches

Endothermic peaks corresponding to starch gelatinization and retrogradation were analyzed in a DSC Q-2000 (TA instruments, Crawley, UK) equipped with a refrigerated cooling system (RCS 40). Prior to the measurements, calibration for enthalpy and temperature was carried out using indium. T_{zero} hermetic aluminum DSC pans (TA-Instruments) were employed. An empty pan was used as reference and dry nitrogen at a flow rate of 50 ml/min, was used as the purge gas. Starch samples (6 mg) were loaded into the aluminum pans and distilled water (18 μ l) was added with

the help of a micro syringe. Samples were hermetically sealed and allowed to equilibrate for 60 min at 30 °C before testing in the DSC instrument. Samples were heated from 30 to 100 °C at 10 °C/min to gelatinize the starch. Pans were rapidly cooled down to room temperature and then stored at 4 °C for 7 days. After 7 days, samples were rescanned from 20°C to 110 °C at 5 °C/min and the onset temperature (T_o), peak temperature (T_p) and conclusion temperature (T_c) as well as the “retrogradation” enthalpy, ΔH_r (expressed as J/g of sample in dry basis) corresponding to the endothermal peak of the retrograded amylopectin (i.e., amylose-amylopectin and amylopectin-amylopectin interactions) were calculated. All samples were run in triplicate.

2.2.3.2 Dynamic rheology of gelatinized and retrograded starch gels

Gel samples (18 % w/w solid content) were prepared in Rapid Visco Analyzer (RVA) canisters by dispersing 5 g of starch into 23 g of distilled water and running the AACC standard 61-02.01 (AACC, 2015) cycle RVA-4 (Perten Instruments Australia, Macquarie Park, Australia). Pasting curves and cold-peak viscosity values are reported in the supplementary material (Fig. S1). Immediately after the RVA cycle, starch gels were poured into plastic circular molds (6 disks of 20 mm diameter and 0.35 mm height), spread out evenly to fill the circular mold and capped with a plastic plate that was bolted to the base of the mold. After 1-hour cooling (i.e., 1-hour after gelatinization in the RVA), the sample was placed in a stress-controlled rheometer (AR 2000 Rheometer, TA Instruments, New Castle, DE, USA) using 100 grit medium sand paper on both the bottom plate and a 20 mm diameter parallel plate geometry to avoid slippage effects. The remaining disks were stored in the sealed plastic molds for 7 days at 4 °C. For rheological testing, the height between plates ranged from 1.5-2.5 mm that varied according to the gel consistency to achieve a normal force of 0.5 N (± 0.5). After height adjustment, the sample edge was covered with vaseline oil to avoid sample drying. The sample was let to relax in the testing position for 10

min to eliminate residual stresses created during the loading process. Two frequency sweeps (at 25 and 85 °C) from 0.1 to 10 Hz and a temperature sweep from 25 to 85 °C at 5 °C/min and a frequency of 1 Hz were performed. The three tests were carried out using a maximum strain up to 2 %, which was previously determined to be within the linear viscoelastic range for all the tested samples. The storage modulus (G'), which represents the solid-like or elastic component of the material, was obtained from the measurements. The value of $\Delta G'$ was calculated from the frequency sweep at 25 °C as the increase of G' valued at a frequency of 1 Hz over the storage time, i.e., G' values at day 7 minus the corresponding G' values at day 1 (1 hour after gelatinization). The drop of G' values during the temperature sweep was calculated as the value of G' measured at 25 °C minus the corresponding value of G' measured at 85 °C and normalized by the value of G' measured at 25 °C, as reported by Roman et al. (2018a). Fig. S2 shows a typical plot obtained from the temperature sweep test. Coefficient of variation among triplicate measurements was generally 13% or less.

2.2.4 *In vitro* starch digestion kinetics

Retrograded gelatinized starch powders were obtained from the remaining gel discs that were not used for the rheology testing at day 1 (1h after starch gelatinization) and day 7, which were immediately freeze-dried and cryo-milled. Selected samples with marked differences in M_w , namely native banana, EB1, EB3, EB6 and EB9, were chosen to perform the *in vitro* digestion analyses. Samples were incubated with 0.2 mU of porcine-pancreatic α -amylase of a high purity per mg of starch using the procedure reported by Sun, Warren, Netzel, and Gidley (2016). 50 mg of retrograded powders were suspended in 10 mL of phosphate buffered saline and incubated at 37 °C with constant stirring at 350 rpm with a 3 mm \times 6 mm magnetic stirrer bar. At defined time intervals, aliquots of 200 μ L were withdrawn into Eppendorf tubes containing 200 μ L of ice-cold

0.3 M sodium carbonate. The tubes were vortex-mixed and centrifuged at 12,000 g for 6 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was used to determine the reducing sugar content using the PAHBAH assay.

The digestion results are expressed as the mean of at least two replicates.

The digestion rate (k) and the equilibrium concentration (C_{∞}) were calculated from the slope ($-k$) and y-intercept, respectively, from the plot of the natural log of the first derivative of concentration respect to time as a function of time as expressed by the following equation (Butterworth, Warren, Grassby, Patel, & Ellis, 2012):

$$\ln\left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial t}\right) = -kt + \ln(C_{\infty}k)$$

2.2.5 Statistical analysis

Statistical differences were studied using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) in the Statgraphics Centurion XVI software (Statpoint Technologies, Inc., Warrenton, USA). Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) was used to describe means with 95% confidence intervals. The individual effects of extrusion parameters on SME were calculated by multiple analysis of variance (MANOVA) using LSD to calculate means with their 95 % confidence intervals.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Specific Mechanical Energy (SME), molecular size and weight of starch molecules

SME is a key process parameter because it is a direct reflection of the impact of the extrusion conditions on the material structural characteristics. It is commonly used to adjust the product conversion, optimize and scale up the extrusion process appropriately. SME is also the parameter most closely related to the shear attained during extrusion (Alvarez-Martinez, Kondury, & Harper, 1988) and can be adjusted, for a given screw configuration, to control process parameters. In this work, specifically feed moisture content and screw speed were modified to obtain different SME values ranging from 177 kJ/kg to 394 kJ/kg (Table1).

Table 2. Individual effects of extrusion parameters on SME.

	Feed moisture content (%)			Screw speed (rpm)		
	22	27	32	120	200	280
SME (kJ/kg)	334c	272b	227a	220a	281b	331c
R_{hsmall} (nm)	24.6b	17.3a	14.5a	23.1b	17.9a	15.4a

Values with different letters in the same row are significantly different with $p < 0.05$.

Detailed information about the individual effects of extrusion parameters on SME was obtained through a multiple analysis of variance (Table 2) and results indicated that higher SME can be produced by decreasing feed moisture content and increasing the screw speed. These results are in agreement with those reported previously for different starchy materials, including sago (Govindasamy, Campanella, & Oates, 1997) and potato starch (Della Valle, Boche, Colonna, & Vergnes, 1995).

The molecular size and molecular weight of the treated starches produced using the 9 extrusion conditions were investigated. The molecular size of amylopectin, as reported by its hydrodynamic radius (R_h), ranged from 102 for native banana starch to 46 nm for sample EB 9 (Table 3). These results indicate that extrusion conditions yielding SME of 394 kJ/kg can decrease R_h of native amylopectin by more than half. This reduction of amylopectin size is similar to that attained in commercial acid-converted starches (Martinez et al., 2018). The molecular weight of amylopectin (M_w) was also assessed using a MALS detector. A typical chromatogram obtained from the MALS detector signal is shown in Fig. 1. It is noted that with the sample concentration and injection volume used in this study and amylose molecules being highly polydispersed, they did not exhibit detectable laser-light scattering signals. This occurrence has been already reported by Yoo and Jane (2002) in starches containing a normal amylose ratio, i.e., those without modified starch biosynthesis. By analyzing M_w , it ranged from 275×10^6 in native banana starch to 4×10^6 g/mol in

the EB 9 sample (Table 3), which is similar to the values reported for fragmented amylopectin of extruded maize starch (Brümmer et al., 2002).

Fig. 1. Example of chromatographs obtained from the Multi Angle Light Scattering detector (MALS) for native and extruded banana starches (EB 3 and EB 9).

Two strong significant correlations were obtained between SME and amylopectin hydrodynamic radius R_h ($R^2=0.81$) and molecular weight M_w ($R^2=0.78$), respectively (Fig. 2). Results showed that both R_h and M_w values decrease linearly with increasing SME and could be easily calculated from a linear regression obtained for the co-rotating twin-screw extruder and the screw configuration used. The regression equation may vary if a different extruder and screw profile is used. A similar linear master curve of SME versus intrinsic viscosity, which is an indicator of M_w using the Mark-Houwink equation, has been already reported for other systems such as wheat starch (Berzin, Tara, Tighzert, & Vergnes, 2010) and waxy wheat flour (Kowalski, Hause, Joyner, & Ganjyal, 2018). Interestingly, Brümmer et al. (2002), extruded maize starch in a co-rotating twin-screw extruder using a screw configuration of similar characteristics to the one used in this research and found a linear decrease of amylopectin M_w with increasing SME up to 150 W.h/kg

(540 kJ/g), after which the M_w became independent of SME reaching a stable molecular weight of approximate 3.5×10^6 g/mol. Similar findings in terms of size were reported in waxy maize by Liu et al. (2010), who reported a size-dependent degradation mechanism of amylopectin molecules in waxy maize down to a stable size of $R_h \sim 50$ nm. Thus, it seems that the size of banana amylopectin achieved with the most severe extrusion conditions (in terms of shear) used in this work might be close to the limit of the degree of amylopectin fragmentation attainable. Further studies on extrusion of starches with amylopectin of different molecular weights and chain length distributions are necessary to further understand the underlying mechanisms affecting these correlations.

Fig. 2. Correlations between molecular weight (A) and hydrodynamic radius (B) of the amylopectin molecules contained in banana starch processed under nine different SME. Native banana starch is not considered for the correlations.

The peak in the SEC size distribution from the RID detector corresponding to starch molecules with a hydrodynamic radius $R_h < 40$ nm was also investigated and the R_h at the peak maximum ranged from 44 for native banana starch to 12 nm for the sample EB 9 (Table 3). It must be noted that a population of highly fragmented amylopectin molecules could co-elute with amylose, since they could have comparable hydrodynamic sizes (Liu et al., 2010; Tran et al., 2011). Therefore, the R_h at the maximum peak is called $R_{h\text{small}}$, which accounts for both amylose and the smallest fraction of fragmented amylopectin molecules. Converse to the correlation found for $R_{h\text{AP}}$, there was no correlation between $R_{h\text{small}}$ and SME (Table 3). A multiple analysis of variance revealed that despite of the higher SME attained with lower feed moisture content, lower shear-induced fragmentation of the small molecules population could have occurred (Table 3). These results clearly indicate that the shear degradation of small molecules is not controlled by the same factors affecting shear degradation of large molecules. It is noted that SME is proportional to three factors:

the average apparent viscosity of the melt, the square of the average shear rate, and the average residence time in the screw-barrel assembly (Bouvier & Campanella 2014). This means that, depending on the relative values of these three factors, different thermomechanical profiles can be obtained for the same SME. Since variations in feed moisture content have been reported to have minimum effects on the mean residence time (Gogoi & Yam 1994), it seems that a high apparent viscosity of the melt could have a protective effect on small molecules to be fragmented by shear.

The shear degradation process has also been identified to be selective towards the molecule branching characteristics. The different susceptibility of amylose and amylopectin to shear degradation has been explained based on their different branching degree. The relatively low flexibility of short amylopectin branches results in a difficult application of shear forces throughout the entire molecule during the process. Additionally, linear amylose molecules are mostly comprised by long chains that can withstand a higher extent of deformation without translating the shear force to the entire molecule (Liu et al. 2010). However, it is still not clear whether amylose is less prone to shear degradation because of its linear nature or its smaller size (Liu et al. 2010). In short, and from results obtained in this work, it appears that molecular fragmentation of amylopectin molecules can be selectively controlled monitoring SME. However, the fragmentation of small molecules cannot be controlled by simply selecting SME, instead, it could be done lowering the apparent viscosity of the melt by incorporating more plasticizer (water in this work). A more complete interpretation of these results would require complementary work at a more fundamental level to investigate the effects of the melt apparent viscosity on the molecular size reduction of amylose molecules as distinct to that of small amylopectin molecules with similar hydrodynamic size.

3.2 Thermal properties of retrograded starch gels

The first temperature scan in the DSC revealed a complete starch gelatinization during extrusion of all samples, as indicated by the absence of endothermic peaks for the melting of native amylopectin double helices (data not shown). In addition, the pasting profile of the extruded banana starches (Fig. S1) also confirmed full gelatinization, as seen by the absence of typical increase in viscosity during heating and the formation of an immediate viscous paste before the slurry is heated (Martinez, Calvino, Rosell, & Gomez, 2014). The height of the cold peak viscosity decreased as SME was increased, which is attributed to the molecular fragmentation described in section 3.1.

During storage of gelatinized starch-based gels, amylopectin chains may re-associate with amylose and other amylopectin chains through the formation of double helices or double helices aggregates (Klucinec & Thompson, 1999). These re-associations are formed either in the same molecule (intra-) or among different molecules (inter-), which may or may not contribute to the elasticity of a gel network (as explained in detail in section 3.3). All the interactions involving amylopectin, which foster a short-range order, can be measured by detecting the heat generated during their melting, which usually happens at around 55 °C (Martinez et al., 2018; Matalanis, Campanella, & Hamaker, 2009; Roman et al., 2018a). Thus, after a 7 days storage in sealed pans, gelatinized banana samples exhibited an endotherm with peak temperature in the range of 58.4-61.0 °C (data not shown) and enthalpies in the range of 5.4 to 6.3 J/g (Table 3).

Table 3. Thermomechanical properties of amylopectin present in native and extruded banana starch.

	R_{hAP} (nm)	R_{hsmall} (nm)	M_w (x10⁶ g/mol)	ΔH_r (J/g)	G' 25 °C day 1 (Pa)	G' 85 °C day 7 (Pa)
Native	102.65h ±0.53	44.62f ±2.02	275.0a ± 67.2	5.40a ±0.05	2907e ±134	2962e ±444
EB 1	58.87g ±1.73	18.01bc ±5.67	17.1b ± 1.7	5.51ab ±0.14	182bc ±73	368ab ±27
EB 2	56.60f ±1.14	13.43a ±1.68	12.7b ± 1.7	5.58ab ±0.05	51a ±12	238a ±106
EB 3	54.27e ±1.47	12.27a ±0.29	9.9b ± 2.4	5.90cd ±0.08	43a ±18	339ab ±58
EB 4	58.31g ±0.99	24.20de ±1.54	13.1b ± 0.7	5.73bc ±0.22	253cd ±39	580bc ±17
EB 5	52.67de ±0.85	15.01ab ±0.10	6.7b ± 0.6	6.15de ±0.02	79ab ±10	398abc ±8
EB 6	51.05cd ±1.09	12.74a ±0.95	6.1b ± 1.9	6.13de ±0.07	106ab ±10	329ab ±14
EB 7	49.55bc ±0.56	27.19e ±0.18	9.8b ± 1.0	6.11de ±0.01	291d ±80	918d ±159
EB 8	48.26b ±1.34	25.24de ±0.68	4.5b ± 0.0	6.12de ±0.29	259cd ±43	967d ±89
EB 9	46.44a ±0.00	21.35cd ±1.42	4.0b ± 0.3	6.25e ±0.14	173bc ±63	700cd ±152

Measured properties were hydrodynamic radius of small molecules (R_{hsmall}) and amylopectin (R_{hAP}), molecular weight (M_w), enthalpy (ΔH_r) attributed to amylopectin retrogradation, and elastic modulus values of gels measured at 25 °C for day 1 (1h after starch gelatinization) and at 85 °C for day 7, respectively. Values with different letters in the same column are significantly different with p <0.05.

Interestingly, the enthalpy of the endothermic peaks showed a negative linear correlation with both M_w (R²= 0.864) and R_{hAP} (R²= 0.860) for the amylopectin molecules of the extruded starch. In particular, this would indicate a marked increase in the propensity of amylopectin branches to form double helices (and/or of already formed double helices to form aggregates) during storage when the molecular weight of the amylopectin molecules decreases (Fig. 3 and Table 3). In addition, it entails that molecular interactions involving amylopectin molecules with amylose (AM-AP) and/or other amylopectin molecules (AP-AP) during storage can be manipulated by selecting extrusion parameters that result in targeted SME and, in turn, targeted M_w that promote those interactions. Although the amylopectin chain length distribution is not modified after extrusion (Li et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2010), it seems that amylopectin fragmentation may improve its mobility and orientation during storage, thus promoting these interactions.

Fig. 3. Relationship between molecular weight (M_w) and retrogradation enthalpy of for amylopectin molecules (ΔH_r) present in extruded banana starch. Native banana starch was not considered for the correlations.

3.3 Dynamic oscillatory rheometry for starch intermolecular associations during storage

It has been hypothesized that during retrogradation, inter-molecular bridges among different starch molecules can be established. These cross-linkages are considered to be present as physical junction zones (PJZ). PJZ are considered to be formed by inter-molecular associations between double helices and/or crystallites formed from aggregates of those double helices (Klucinec & Thompson, 1999). In 1953, Flory recognized that some molecular chains do not contribute to the elasticity of a gel network. Considering a more recent adaptation of the Flory's approach to starch systems (Klucinec & Thompson, 1999), and the most accepted model to describe the starch structure (Bertoft, 2013), molecular chains in a starch gel system can be classified as internal and terminal. Internal chains within a gel structure extend from one PJZ to the next one occurring along a given primary molecule, whereas terminal chains are bound at one end to a PJZ and terminated as a free end. Thus, the PJZ among chains can also be divided into internal and terminal. In other words, internal PJZ join more than two internal elements, while terminal PJZ

join an internal element to a terminal one [detailed schematics of these arrangements are reported by Klucinec and Thompson (2002)]. Importantly, starch chains have the capacity to retrograde along internal chains without the formation of a new internal PJZ. Additionally, terminal chains also have the capacity to retrograde. In other words, starch retrogradation would contribute to high measured enthalpy of retrogradation ΔH_r for the gels but not necessarily to their G' development. Conversely, only internal PJZ through retrogradation are responsible for the mechanical properties of the starch gel and ultimately responsible for the gel physical properties such as texture and syneresis. The overall formation of internal PJZ involving AM and/or AP molecules was studied through the increase of G' values after 7-day storage (light grey bars in Fig. 4A).

Fig. 4. (A) Increase of G' values (light grey bars) at 1 Hz and 25 °C from day 1 to day 7 ($\Delta G'$) and relative drop of G' (dark grey bars) measured at 1Hz in a temperature sweep from 25 °C to 85 °C of starch gels at day 7. (B) Correlations between values of G' at a frequency of 1 Hz, temperature 25 °C and 1 day storage (dark grey dots) and values of G' measured at 1Hz, 85 °C and 7 days storage (light grey dots) with the hydrodynamic radius of the small molecules population (R_{hsmall}). Native banana starch was not considered for the correlations.

In regard to amylopectin molecules and despite of the observed negative linear relationship between the amount of overall interactions (measured by ΔH_r) and molecular size (Fig. 3), it appears that the extrusion process is promoting a significant decrease on the $\Delta G'$ values compared to the native counterpart (Fig. 4A). This result would suggest that the extrusion process is able to produce starch molecules that lead to a lower total number of internal PJZ involving either/both AM and AP molecules upon retrogradation. A more insightful explanation for this phenomenon can be given by additional rheological indicators providing information about 1) AM-AM interactions, associated with G' values of starch gels measured at 25 °C after 1 day storage and G' values of gels measured at 85 °C after 7 storage (Table 3 and Fig. 4B) and 2) internal PJZ involving

AP molecules determined by the measurement of the relative G' drop in the temperature sweep after 7 storage (dark grey bars in Fig. 4A).

Regarding AM-AM interactions, G' values of gels without storage measured at 25 °C, which are associated with rapid starch re-associations usually involving AM starch molecules, were highly correlated ($R^2=0.930$) with R_{hsmall} (Fig. 4B). Likewise, a positive linear correlation ($R^2=0.835$) was found between R_{hsmall} and G' values of gels measured at 85 °C after 7 days storage (Fig. 4B), the latter indicating only contributions of thermostable AM-AM interactions (Klucinec & Thompson, 1999). These results would confirm that AM fragmentation is attained during extrusion and is a key factor affecting the mechanical properties of the gels (e.g., gel development).

Additionally, internal PJZ involving AP molecules were also investigated through the temperature sweep test on retrograded gels stored for 7 days (see Fig. S2). In the test, a decrease of G', resulting from the melting of AM-AP and/or AP-AP internal PJZ, described as relative G' drop, was observed for all samples (Fig. 4A). Results showed an increase in the propensity of extruded AP to form internal PJZ compared to the native counterpart, which can be attributed to the higher propensity of smaller molecules to get in proximity promoting those junctions. Klucinec and Thompson (2002) already suggested that smaller AP molecules are more prone to the formation of PJZ that helps to build gel structures. However, it seems that there is a molecular size/weight threshold from which this effect is slightly neutralized. From a textural quality point of view, although the propensity of AP molecules to form AM-AP and/or AP-AP PJZ is in general improved through extrusion, gels became weaker because of a lower propensity of amylose molecules to form AM-AM interactions. In fact, among all the extruded samples, the relative G' values drop was lower at higher SME, so it seems that after a certain size reduction, the propensity

of AP molecules to form new internal PJZ does not increase (Fig. 4A). A simplified schematic of the suggested mechanism is depicted in Fig. 5. These results seem to indicate that shear-induced fragmentation of the AP molecules improves fragment mobility and chances to get in closer proximity with other molecules upon cooling and storage, but at the same time, it would reduce its effective length to join two internal elements that build network structures. This structural transformation will enable the use of extruded flours as means of improvement the physical quality of some foods, such as the delay of bread hardness/staling (Martinez, Marcos, & Gomez, 2013) and sauce syneresis (Roman, Reguilon, & Gomez, 2018b).

Fig. 5. Schematic of double helix formation through retrogradation of whole amylopectin (AP) (from A to B) and fragmented AP after high shear extrusion (from A' to C'). AM is not considered to simplify the schematic. Theoretical newly formed double helices are depicted as red cylinders.

In this schematic representation, shear-induced fragmentation resulted in the formation of 2 extra double helices due to the higher mobility of smaller size AP molecules and their higher chances to get in proximity. This would result in 4 less free chains that otherwise would be available as rapid digestible substrates for α -amylase. It must be noted that, the formation of newly AP interactions would not necessarily affect negatively the mechanical properties of the gels, and ultimately a food product, since the effective length to bring together two internal elements that build gel-like structures would be reduced.

3.4 *In vitro* starch digestion kinetics

Experimental starch digestion curves of all samples are depicted in Fig. 6. All samples, regardless of storage time, were digested following an exponential curve. In fact, experimental LOS plots (Fig. S3) yielded a single digestion rate (k) over the incubation time performed with pancreatic α -amylase. This outcome suggests that all samples contain fractions that do not differ in digestion rate over time. The *in vitro* digestion kinetic parameters in fully gelatinized material without storage (1h after gelatinization) and after a 7-day storage period after fitting to the LOS model are reported in Table 4. No significant differences were found in the starch digestion rate (k) and extension (C_∞) among samples without storage (analyzed 1 hour after cooking). Interestingly, although all samples exhibited a decrease in C_∞ with storage, only samples EB 3, EB 6 and EB9 showed a significant decrease of k . More specifically, k values after 7-day storage for samples EB 3, EB 6 and EB 9 were up to 36 % lower than those of both native banana and sample EB1.

Fig. 6. *In vitro* starch digestograms of gelatinized starch gels from native and extruded banana starches (samples EB1, EB3, EB6 and EB9) after 1 day (1-hour after starch gelatinization) and 7 days storage.

These results support our recent investigations showing that, the propensity of amylopectin molecules to form SSDS could be further improved by a reduction of their molecular size by either extrusion (Roman et al., 2019) and acid-conversion (Martinez et al., 2018). However, the chains segments resulting in the slow digestion property remained still unclear. Looking at G' drop values (Fig. 4A), EB1 exhibited significantly more AM-AP and/or AP-AP internal PJZ compared to native banana starch, which, interestingly, did not affect starch digestion rate. Conversely, EB1 and EB3, the latter with significantly lower digestion rate, showed no differences in the G' drop values. Meanwhile, the decrease in k agrees with an increase in the enthalpy for amylopectin

retrogradation (Table 3), which accounts for any type of interaction involving AP in terms of gel structure, i.e., internal and terminal PJZ. As depicted in Fig. 5, the shear-induced fragmentation of starch molecules would improve their mobility and chances to get in closer proximity with other starch molecules, but at the same time would reduce its effective length to join two internal elements that build network structures. This is an important finding since it demonstrates that the creation of SSDS starch through retrogradation does not necessarily influence negatively the mechanical properties (gel development) of food systems, which is paramount in certain food applications.

It must be noted that this effect may not be universal for all starches and will depend on their chain length distribution. This was precisely the rationale for selecting banana starch in the current, and a previous study (Roman et al., 2019). Banana amylopectin exhibits a higher proportion of long chains (long to short chain molar ratio = 0.73) and short branches with an average length of 17.0 GU, which are structural features heavily involved in molecular interactions during retrogradation resulting in slowly digested starch systems (Martinez, et al., 2018; Syahariza, Sar, Hasjim, Tizzotti & Gilbert, 2013; Roman et al., 2019; Zhang & Hamaker, 2012;). Results also show that there is a minimum reduction of amylopectin molecular size that may result in a further increase of SSDS. Specifically, banana amylopectin molecules with R_{hAP} and M_w of 54.3 nm and 9.9×10^6 g/mol (EB3) exhibited higher propensity to form SDS through retrogradation compared to EB1 and native banana starch. In other words, the R_h and M_w threshold resulting in the formation of SDS is a range between 54.3 and 58.9 nm and 9.9×10^6 and 17.1×10^6 g/mol, respectively, which in the currently used co-rotating twin-screw extruder was attained in a SME range between 177 and 274 kJ/Kg.

Table 4. Effects of the extrusion treatment in the *in vitro* digestion rate and extent of starch gels analyzed 1 hour after starch gelatinization (day 1) and after 7-days storage.

	Day 1		Day 7	
	k (min ⁻¹)	C _∞ (%)	k (min ⁻¹)	C _∞ (%)
Native	0.035aA ±0.001	42.85aB ±2.06	0.034bA ±0.004	25.32abA ±2.32
EB 1	0.041aA ±0.001	39.80aB ±1.46	0.040bA ±0.004	20.70aA ±0.45
EB 3	0.041aB ±0.001	40.77aB ±3.13	0.022aA ±0.001	28.84bA ±1.86
EB 6	0.040aB ±0.001	47.62aB ±8.71	0.026aA ±0.001	28.48bA ±1.67
EB 9	0.039aB ±0.001	44.51aB ±4.59	0.025aA ±0.001	29.17bA ±3.35

Values followed by the same lowercase letters within each parameter (column) indicate no significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$). Values followed by the same uppercase letters within each sample (row) indicate no significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between day 1 and day 7.

4 Conclusions

Processed starchy foods, owing to the amorphous stage of the starch molecules are characterized for having high glycemic indexes and consequently considered of low nutritional value. A promising strategy to solve this problem is the selection and manipulation of the starch structure at the molecular level to result in targeted self-assemblies that are slowly digested. For the first-time, this work provides a mechanistic evidence about the feasibility of extrusion technology to create structurally-driven slowly digestible starch (SSDS) through retrogradation. Here, it is shown that the nature of the formed SSDS is mostly consisting of molecular assemblies involving amylopectin and their fragments that do not necessarily bring deleterious effects on the food mechanical properties that may affect its texture quality. It is demonstrated that interactions

promoting those molecular assemblies can be further increased by shear-induced reduction of the hydrodynamic radius (R_h) and molecular weight (M_w) of amylopectin molecules in a range between 54.3 and 58.9 nm and 9.9×10^6 and 17.1×10^6 g/mol, respectively. Results of this work are also expected to contribute to the improvement of the sustainability of food systems through technology developments that are energy efficient, do not use chemicals and do not produce wastes to process sustainable resources such as banana starch. Banana starch comes from an unexploited by-product (banana pulp) and, in this work, is demonstrated its enormous nutritional potential using a clean and low-cost technology.

Supporting information

Additional figures are available for supporting data. These include the pasting profile of native and extruded flours (Fig. S1), example of a G' drop during a temperature sweep of starch gels stored for 7 days (Fig. S2), and example of a LOS plot obtained from the digestion curve (Fig. S3).

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Abbreviations

AM, amylose; AP, amylopectin; C_∞ , equilibrium concentration; DSC, Differential Scanning Calorimeter; EB, extruded banana; G' , elastic modulus; k , digestion rate; LOS, Log of Slope; MALS, Multi Angle Light Scattering; M_w , molecular weight; PAHBAH, 4-Hydroxybenzhydrazide; PJZ, Physical Junction Zone; ΔH_r , Enthalpy of Retrogradation; R_h ,

hydrodynamic radius; RID, Refractive Index Detector; RS, resistant starch; RVA, Rapid Visco Analyzer; SDS, slowly digestible starch; SEC, Size Exclusion Chromatography; SME, Specific Mechanical Energy; SSDS, Structurally-driven SDS; V_h , Hydrodynamic Volume.

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